

CITY OF IRVINE

Sustainability Commission

CLIMATE CRISIS ACTION REPORT

A Report in Observance of Earth Day 2026

An update to the April 2021 report to the Green Ribbon Environmental Committee, "Physical and Financial Potential of a Solar-Powered Irvine"

By

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Presented to:

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The Irvine City Council

The Irvine Sustainability Commission

April 22, 2026

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Executive Summary

I submit this report to the Mayor, the City Council, and my colleagues on the Sustainability Commission on the occasion of Earth Day 2026. It is an update to the report I wrote in April 2021 for the Green Ribbon Environmental Committee (GREC) on the physical and financial potential of a solar-powered Irvine, revised and broadened five years later with the benefit of the City's 2019 Greenhouse Gas Inventory, the September 2025 Public Draft of the Climate Action and Adaptation Plan (CAAP), and the continuing advance of the technologies, financing tools, and state programs that make my original conclusions even more achievable today than they were then.

I write in the conviction that the City of Irvine, as a community, as a government, and as a civic tradition, has both the obligation and the capacity to act decisively on the climate crisis. Our own emissions are accelerating the crisis. Deferring responsibility to the county, state, federal, or international levels is, in my view, no longer a defensible posture for a city of Irvine's sophistication, means, and ethical leadership.

Taking the 2021 ACHIEVES Resolution (Resolution No. 21-50) as my foundation, and drawing on the 2019 GHG Inventory and the draft CAAP, I identify three actions the City can take now that, together, would retire the overwhelming majority of Irvine's community-wide greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions:

1. Immediately halt new natural gas infrastructure installation and begin an orderly transition of existing gas loads to electric alternatives.
2. Scale the One Irvine program into a universal, city-financed Solarize-and-Electrify revolving loan, delivering rooftop solar, battery storage, heat-pump water heating and space conditioning, and electric vehicle (EV) charging to every willing household at zero upfront cost, repayable at property transfer. This is a direct generalization of the revolving-fund concept I proposed in my 2021 report.
3. Accelerate transportation electrification through municipal financing for resident EV purchases, aggressive deployment of DC fast charging at city parks and multi-family sites, and an honest, electric-bus-forward redesign of the Irvine CONNECT shuttle so that it becomes a net carbon reducer rather than, as I show in Section 2.3, a net carbon emitter.

I include an appendix documenting how recent decisions by the California Public Utilities Commission (CPUC), specifically the retroactive revision of the Power Charge Indifference Adjustment (PCIA) methodology under Decision 25-06-049, have shifted costs away from investor-owned utility (IOU) customers and onto Community Choice Energy (CCE) customers. This regulatory capture is, in my judgment, the primary driver of the current, temporary increase in OCPA rates and is the single greatest external threat to the City's decarbonization pathway. The City of Irvine, Orange County, and our state delegation must push back as one.

Section 3 of this report addresses a question that arises naturally in any discussion of climate strategy: whether the City can offset its emissions by planting more trees. The Urban Forest Master Plan (UFMP) is

a valuable program, but the arithmetic of tree sequestration is unambiguous. Offsetting Irvine’s community-wide emissions through tree planting alone would require on the order of 75 million new trees every year, against a UFMP planting target of 1,900 per year. Trees are a meaningful co-benefit; they are not a climate lever at the scale the ACHIEVES Resolution requires.

None of this is easy. All of it is possible. The question before us is not whether Irvine can lead, but whether Irvine will.

1. Introduction

1.1 The Moral Imperative to Act Locally

The climate crisis is no longer a distant scientific projection. It is the lived experience of wildfires in the foothills east of Irvine, of ocean acidification off our coast, of heat waves that strain our grid, and of drought that shapes our water policy. The 2018 Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) special report identified a remaining carbon budget of 420 gigatonnes of CO₂ to retain a 67 percent chance of limiting warming to 1.5 °C. When I wrote my 2021 report, three years' worth of emissions had already consumed a substantial share of that budget; five years later, less than half of it remains.

Every metric ton of carbon dioxide emitted within the City of Irvine contributes to that depletion. The natural gas burned in Irvine homes and businesses, the unspecified-source electricity purchased for Irvine residents, and the gasoline combusted on Irvine roads all add to the atmospheric load that is destabilizing the climate system. Deferring responsibility to the county, state, federal, or international levels, with the reasoning that Irvine's contribution is small in global terms, is an abdication of responsibility that no local government of Irvine's ethical leadership, financial resources, and civic capability can defensibly make.

Irvine is not a typical American city. It was the first city in the nation to ban chlorofluorocarbons, a measure credited with catalyzing the recovery of the stratospheric ozone layer: an effort led by Mayor Larry Agran in 1989, in his role as mayor then. Irvine is home to one of the world's great research universities, where I serve on the faculty. It sits at the heart of one of the most economically productive regions on Earth. The tools, the science, the public will, and the financial resources to lead on climate are all present here. What is required is the political courage to act at the scale and pace the science demands.

1.2 Authorship and Scope¹

I write this report as a Commissioner on the City of Irvine Sustainability Commission, a member of the University of California, Irvine faculty in the Department of Physics and Astronomy, and—most importantly for present purposes—as an Irvine resident who has worked on the question of the City's climate obligations since 2019. It is submitted on the occasion of Earth Day 2026 and should be read as a commissioner's perspective intended to stimulate discussion, not as an adopted position of the Commission or the City.

This report draws on several prior bodies of work: my April 2021 report to the Green Ribbon Environmental Committee, "Physical and Financial Potential of a Solar-Powered Irvine;" the 2019 community-wide and municipal GHG Emissions Inventory prepared for the City by Ascent Environmental and released in June 2023; the September 2025 Public Draft of Irvine's Climate Action and Adaptation

¹ In preparing this report, I used Anthropic's Claude (Claude Opus 4.7) as a drafting and research assistant for literature review, preliminary prose drafting, and figure generation. All analysis, conclusions, recommendations, and final text are my own.

Plan; and research published by myself and others in the intervening years. I am grateful to the city staff, fellow commissioners, and city contractors whose work has made this update possible.

1.3 The ACHIEVES Resolution (Resolution No. 21-50)

In 2021, the same year I submitted my earlier report, the Irvine City Council adopted Resolution No. 21-50, the ACHIEVES Resolution, under the leadership of Councilmember Kathleen Treseder, formally committing the City to address climate change in its environment, values, and energy sources. The Resolution commits the City to endeavor to achieve a zero-carbon local economy consistent with 2030 targets based on the most recent climate science. Specific commitments include:

- Development of a CEQA-qualified Climate Action and Adaptation Plan with detailed deadlines for science-based GHG reductions.
- Active pursuit of environmental, economic, and social justice in climate action.
- New codes, standards, and incentives so that all new and existing buildings, public and private, become energy-efficient and zero-carbon.
- Ambitious mode-share targets for biking, walking, and transit; expanded zero-emission vehicles; accessible public transit; and land-use practices that reduce vehicle miles traveled.
- 100 percent renewable energy in municipal operations and 100 percent renewable electricity offered to residents and businesses through the Orange County Power Authority (OCPA).
- Planning, permitting, and building of critical energy infrastructure, including EV charging networks, grid upgrades for electrification of heating and transport, microgrids, and renewable fuel transport and storage.
- Development of an innovation toolkit for carbon-free energy technologies.

In my view, the ACHIEVES Resolution is the foundational policy instrument against which every subsequent climate action of the City should be measured. The ambition of the 2030 timeline is extraordinary. It is also important if Irvine is to honor its commitment to the Paris Climate Agreement.

1.4 The 2019 Greenhouse Gas Inventory

The Draft Greenhouse Gas Emissions Inventory Report for the City of Irvine Climate Action and Adaptation Plan, prepared by Ascent Environmental and released in June 2023, provides the first formal, peer-reviewed accounting of the City's emissions. Based on 2019 activity data, the inventory finds total community-wide emissions of approximately 2.25 million metric tons of carbon dioxide equivalent (MTCO₂e). The three sectors I focused on in my 2021 report—electricity, natural gas for heating, and personal transportation—together account for more than 88 percent of that total. The municipal government's own operations, by contrast, contribute less than 1 percent, which tells us plainly that the

City's role in climate action is primarily one of enabling community-wide change rather than solving the problem through its own facilities alone.

1.5 The Draft Climate Action and Adaptation Plan (September 2025)

The Public Draft of the Irvine Climate Action and Adaptation Plan (CAAP), released in September 2025, establishes local GHG reduction targets of 44 percent below 2019 levels by 2030 and 90 percent below 2019 levels by 2040. It is organized around seven strategy areas, including clean energy for buildings, transportation electrification, transit system improvement, solid waste reduction, water efficiency, and climate adaptation. The CAAP represents substantial technical work and commits the City to measurable progress. It is, however, a document written for feasibility rather than urgency. The 44 percent 2030 target is roughly half of what the underlying science, and the ACHIEVES Resolution itself, requires. In this report I propose a complementary set of accelerated actions, consistent with the CAAP's own measures but scaled to the ambition of the original Resolution.

1.6 My 2021 Report: Physical and Financial Potential of a Solar-Powered Irvine

In April 2021 I submitted a report to the City's Green Ribbon Environmental Committee examining whether Irvine's rooftop solar resource could meet the City's residential energy demand, and whether the financial structure of such a transition was feasible. I reached three conclusions that, revisiting the analysis now, I believe hold up well and remain directly relevant to the City's 2026 decisions.

First, the annual solar resource falling on Irvine's residential rooftops exceeds the total annual residential energy demand, for electricity, transportation, and heating combined, by nearly a factor of two. The physical resource is abundant. Second, at the photovoltaic system costs I cited then (and which have continued to decline), rooftop solar delivers electricity at a levelized cost well below retail residential electricity rates in California. The financial case is strong and getting stronger. Third, the principal obstacle to widespread residential solar adoption is the upfront cost of installation, a barrier that a municipal revolving-fund loan program can entirely eliminate without drawing down the City's general fund in the long run.

In 2021, I estimated total residential energy demand at 7.95 petajoules (PJ) per year, of which approximately 41 percent came from natural gas, 31 percent from transportation, and 27 percent from electricity. The 2019 City-commissioned inventory, prepared independently and using utility-supplied data, is in striking agreement with my residential natural gas estimate (I estimated 3.30 PJ, or roughly 31 million therms; the inventory measured 32.85 million therms). This agreement between two independent estimates strengthens confidence in both the scale of the problem and the scale of the opportunity.

My 2021 report was necessarily limited in scope. It focused on the residential sector, on rooftop solar as the dominant renewable resource, and on the financial architecture of a revolving fund. This present

report broadens that analysis in three ways: it brings the non-residential sector explicitly into scope; it extends the revolving-fund concept from solar installation alone to a full Solarize-and-Electrify package including battery storage, heat pumps, and EV charging; and it addresses the transportation sector, which I had treated more briefly in 2021, in substantially greater depth.

1.7 Scope of This Report

Section 2 examines the three largest sectors of Irvine’s emissions profile, natural gas, electricity, and on-road transportation, in light of both the 2019 GHG Inventory and my 2021 GREC report, and recommends specific actions for each. Section 3 closes with a motivational conclusion. An appendix documents the regulatory mechanics by which investor-owned utilities have, with CPUC support, shifted costs onto CCE customers, and recommends advocacy positions for the City, the County, and the state delegation.

2. Reading the GHG Inventory: Common Findings and Required Actions

The 2019 community-wide inventory and my 2021 GREC report, though prepared by different authors with different methodologies, arrive at the same headline conclusion. Irvine’s emissions come from three sources, in roughly the following proportions:

Sector	2019 MTCO ₂ e	Share of Total	Primary Lever
On-road transportation	1,144,205	51%	Electrify vehicles
Electricity (residential + non-residential)	501,715	22%	100% renewable
Natural gas (residential + non-residential)	335,322	15%	Eliminate use
Backup generators (non-residential)	4,507	<1%	Battery backup
Off-road vehicles, waste, water, wastewater	~262,000	12%	Sector-specific
Community total	2,247,593	100%	

Table 1. Source: Draft GHG Emissions Inventory Report (Ascent Environmental, June 2023), 2019 activity data.

I discuss the three priority sectors in turn below. In each case the required action is substantive, but the pathway is already identified in the CAAP and, crucially, is consistent with the conclusions I reached in 2021. My contribution in this update is to press for pace and scale commensurate with the ACHIEVES Resolution.

2.1 Natural Gas: Eliminate, Starting Now

The time to stop burning natural gas is immediately.

Natural gas is often treated as the climate problem’s mild cousin, a fossil fuel, yes, but comparatively clean, comparatively cheap, comparatively familiar. This framing is wrong. Burning natural gas in Irvine homes and businesses released an estimated 335,322 MTCO₂e in 2019, with an additional 4,507 MTCO₂e from non-residential backup generators. Unlike transportation and electricity emissions, which are partly mitigated by state-level regulation, natural gas combustion occurs at the point of use (in kitchens, laundry rooms, basements, and mechanical rooms) releasing not only CO₂ but also nitrogen oxides, fine particulate matter, and volatile organic compounds directly into the spaces where our residents live, work, and raise their children. Recent peer-reviewed research has documented substantial methane leakage from the upstream gas system and from appliances themselves, including when those appliances are

turned off. The traditional air-pollution case against indoor gas combustion is, on its own, sufficient to justify action.

Recommended action: halt new natural gas infrastructure.

The City must immediately end the extension and expansion of natural gas infrastructure in its jurisdiction. The legal mechanisms are challenging but not impossible. All-electric reach codes for new residential and commercial buildings remain an available policy tool in California, though jurisdictions have had to adapt their approaches following the Ninth Circuit’s 2023 decision invalidating Berkeley’s gas infrastructure ordinance. *Many cities continue to adopt all-electric or electric-preferred building standards under state building code authority, structured to avoid federal preemption risks.* I recommend that the City pursue an all-electric reach code, an electrification standard for substantial remodels, and a standing policy that no City-owned facility is ever retrofitted or built with new natural gas service. Where existing gas infrastructure serves a City facility, it should be scheduled for retirement at the next equipment end-of-life.

For the existing building stock, the primary policy tool is financing. Heat-pump water heaters, heat-pump space conditioning, induction cooktops, and heat-pump clothes dryers are all mature, available, and at cost parity or better over a full equipment lifetime. The One Irvine program’s green home grants for pre-1976 homes are an excellent foundation. The remaining gap is a financing instrument that makes these upgrades accessible at zero upfront cost for every Irvine household that wants them. That instrument, a scaled version of the revolving fund I proposed in 2021, now extended beyond solar alone, is described in the next section.

2.2 Electricity: 100% Renewable, Locally Generated Where Possible

Why electricity is the keystone of decarbonization.

Switching Irvine’s residents and businesses to 100 percent renewable electricity is the single fastest decarbonization step available to the City, for three reasons I find it worth restating: First, electricity purchasing can be changed through administrative action rather than equipment replacement; a household enrolled in 100 percent renewable service decarbonizes its grid-sourced electricity immediately, not over a twenty-year equipment cycle. Second, every building-sector and transportation-sector electrification measure (heat pumps, induction cooking, electric vehicles) produces clean outcomes only if the electricity driving them is clean; electricity is therefore the keystone on which all other decarbonization rests. Third, rooftop and local solar generation produces no combustion emissions, no fuel imports, and no rate-base risk to the fuel cost volatility that investor-owned utilities routinely pass through to ratepayers.

The Orange County Power Authority (OCPA).

OCPA is the only mechanism currently available for Irvine residents and businesses to purchase 100 percent renewable electricity at scale. The City’s original decision to join OCPA in 2020 and to default its

own operations and community to the 100 percent renewable tier was, in my view, among the most consequential climate actions the City has ever taken. It must be defended and built upon.

Defending OCPA in 2026 requires two things. First, OCPA's 100 percent renewable tier must be financially competitive with, and ideally less expensive than, Southern California Edison's default offering, so that cost pressure drives Irvine customers to the most renewable tier. This is not achievable under current regulatory conditions, not because OCPA's generation costs are high, but because of the Power Charge Indifference Adjustment and related IOU-favoring fee structures discussed in the appendix. Second, I recommend that the City actively oppose those fee structures at every available venue and in coordination with all 24 of California's Community Choice Aggregators.

An unfortunate circumstance must be addressed here. OCPA's lowest-cost tier, Basic Choice, is not a climate product. Its 2024 Power Content Label reported 942 lbs CO₂e per MWh, substantially higher than SCE's standard power mix in 2024 at 515 lbs CO₂e per MWh, driven by a heavy reliance on unspecified-source power in Basic Choice's generation portfolio. The gap from 2023 Power Content Labels show this gap is widening further. I recommend that the City ensure its own accounts, and its outreach to residents and businesses, recommend enrollment in the 100 percent Renewable Choice tier, not Basic Choice, and that it work with OCPA's Board to improve the carbon content of every tier over time. The CAAP's Measure BE-3.1, which sets the goal of enrolling 100 percent of communitywide accounts in 100 percent renewable OCPA service, is the correct policy.

A scaled One Irvine: the Solarize-and-Electrify Revolving Loan Program.

The One Irvine program, described at cityofirvine.org/one-irvine, currently provides small green home grants of up to \$1,500 for pre-1976 single-family homes and condominiums, plus complementary resources for renters. These are meaningful but are, in financial terms, a demonstration project. To meet the timeline of the ACHIEVES Resolution, I believe One Irvine must be scaled into a universal revolving-loan program offering every Irvine homeowner the following package at zero upfront cost:

- Rooftop photovoltaic solar sized to the household's annual electric load.
- Battery storage sized for evening peak and resilience during grid outages.
- Heat-pump water heater and heat-pump space conditioning.
- Induction cooktop and heat-pump clothes dryer.
- Level 2 EV charging circuit and smart panel as needed.

This is a direct extension of the revolving-fund architecture I proposed in 2021: a municipal revolving-fund loan covers the upfront installation cost; the loan is secured against the property as a voluntary tax assessment; and it is repaid through modest annual property-tax-bill charges over the loan term, or as a single balloon payment at sale of the property. Because household monthly energy-bill savings substantially exceed the annual loan repayment, participating households experience positive monthly cash flow from the first month of operation. Because the loan is secured against the property, not the

individual, there is no credit-check barrier and no transfer-at-sale complication; the remaining balance is simply paid at closing by the seller or, by agreement, assumed by the buyer.

In 2021 I estimated that roughly 50,000 Irvine single-family homes remained to be solarized, with roughly 3,600 installations per year required to complete the program by the 2030 target. Including attached single-family homes (townhomes and row houses) that typically retain individual roof ownership, the addressable stock is closer to 60,000 to 65,000 homes. Adding commercial and City-owned rooftops, plus parking-lot canopy installations and battery-only installations for multi-family and renter households, the practical target for a universal program is broader still.

Twenty-year return on investment and the estimated capital recycling horizon.

A typical single-family Irvine home pursuing the full package (solar, battery, heat-pump water heater, heat-pump HVAC, induction cooktop, Level 2 EV charging) can reasonably be expected to realize a twenty-year **net benefit on the order of \$100,000**, net of loan repayment. This figure is driven by avoided retail electricity purchases at current California residential rates, avoided natural gas purchases, avoided gasoline purchases (where an EV is part of the package), and the resilience and property-value benefits of on-site storage. **Extended across roughly 100,000 Irvine households** potentially eligible for some combination of the full package, **the aggregate twenty-year benefit to Irvine residents approaches \$10 billion**. I want to emphasize the character of this benefit: it is a transfer of wealth away from out-of-state fossil-fuel suppliers and IOU shareholders and toward Irvine households, retained and reinvested in the local economy.

The average duration a revolving-fund loan will remain outstanding before repayment is governed by California housing tenure. Recent Redfin research finds that the median U.S. homeowner in 2024 stayed in their home for approximately 11.8 years, while California tenures are substantially longer; in the Los Angeles metropolitan area, median tenure is often estimated in the high-teens to around twenty years. This difference is widely attributed in significant part to the property-tax incentives created by Proposition 13, which reduce turnover by increasing the tax cost of moving. Irvine's owner-occupied housing stock, characterized by stable, high-income ownership and elevated home values, likely reflects or exceeds the Los Angeles median. For revolving-fund planning purposes, I recommend assuming an average loan outstanding period of approximately 18 years, with substantial dispersion. This informs the required initial capital pool: if the City aims to finance 3,600 installations per year at an average fully-packaged cost of \$40,000 per home, the resulting annual lending volume is approximately \$144 million. Sustaining this deployment rate with an 18-year average loan duration implies a required capital pool on the order of \$2.5 to \$2.7 billion. For sensitivity, this requirement would fall to roughly \$2.2 billion at a 15-year average duration and rise to approximately \$2.9 billion at a 20-year duration. A combination of a green municipal bond issuance, federal Greenhouse Gas Reduction Fund partnerships, Inflation Reduction Act tax-credit transfer, and private-sector lending participation, as structured in Berkeley's Berkeley FIRST program, Montpelier's Net Zero Revolving Loan Fund, and the Texas LoanSTAR program, provides well-documented pathways to assembling this capital.

Precedents: revolving-loan solar programs in other American cities.

The concept of a municipal revolving-fund loan program for residential solar and efficiency is neither new nor speculative. Berkeley FIRST, launched in 2008, was the first modern Property Assessed Clean Energy (PACE) program in the nation and has since been widely replicated. Montpelier, Vermont operates a Net Zero Revolving Loan Fund, initially seeded with approximately \$20,000 of city reserve funds and matched by Efficiency Vermont, with energy savings repaid into the fund so that it grows over time. The City of Plano, Texas operates a Smart Energy Loan Program, a U.S. Department of Energy–supported residential efficiency financing initiative, which (according to program materials summarized by GoSolarTexas) is projected to support up to 1,365 residential projects totaling approximately \$7 million in value over a ten-year period. The Solar and Energy Loan Fund (SELF) in Florida provides low-cost financing to income-qualified households for solar and efficiency upgrades. The LoanSTAR program administered by the Texas State Energy Conservation Office provides low-interest revolving loans for public-sector facilities and has deployed hundreds of millions of dollars over multiple decades. These examples demonstrate that revolving energy-investment models are well established across a range of scales and institutional contexts. While program design must be tailored to California law and local fiscal constraints, there is no evident structural barrier to Irvine operating a substantially larger and more ambitious version of such a program. Irvine’s advantages, a strong credit profile, a wealthy and sophisticated population, a favorable solar resource, and a supportive state policy environment, suggest that it is well positioned to lead rather than follow.

2.3 Transportation: Electrify the Hardest Sector

On-road transportation is the single largest source of Irvine’s GHG emissions, contributing 1,144,205 MTCO₂e in 2019, more than half of all community-wide emissions. It is also the hardest sector to decarbonize, because unlike electricity and building energy, the emitting equipment is privately owned, individually purchased, and replaced on decadal cycles. The City cannot directly retire an individual resident’s gasoline vehicle. It can, however, do four things: help finance the transition, deploy public charging where it is most needed, decarbonize the City fleet and its supported shuttle services, and design its land use and streets to reduce vehicle miles traveled in the first place.

Municipal financing for resident EV purchases.

Direct municipal financing of resident EV purchases is uncommon but not unprecedented. Most California programs providing financial assistance for EV purchases operate at the state or regional level, most prominently the Clean Cars 4 All program, which offers up to approximately \$12,000 toward a new or pre-owned EV for income-eligible Californians who retire an older internal-combustion vehicle, with additional financing assistance available. Several municipal utilities offer supplemental rebates in the \$500 to \$1,500 range for EV purchases, including the Los Angeles Department of Water and Power, Pasadena Water and Power, and Alameda Municipal Power, among others. San José Clean Energy has offered enhanced incentives of up to approximately \$4,000 for new or pre-owned EVs in targeted programs. Direct

municipal low-interest EV loan programs are relatively uncommon; instead, financing is typically provided through state-supported initiatives and Community Development Financial Institution (CDFI) partnerships that offer low-interest loans to income-qualified households in participating regions.

I find no record of a California municipality that currently offers its own city-originated EV purchase loans to its residents. Irvine has an opportunity to be the first. A city-financed EV loan program, structured analogously to the Solarize-and-Electrify revolving fund I described in the previous section, could provide low-interest loans for new and pre-owned EV purchases, secured by the vehicle and repayable through utility-bill-pay or property-tax-bill-pay mechanisms for homeowners. The program could be designed to stack with, rather than duplicate, state and federal incentives, and could include specific provisions for low- and moderate-income households and for residents of multi-family buildings who cannot otherwise access home charging.

Fast EV charging at every city park and multi-family site.

Public DC fast charging is the most effective public investment the City can make in transportation decarbonization, and is particularly critical for residents of multi-family housing who lack access to in-home charging. The California Electric Vehicle Infrastructure Project (CALeVIP), funded by the California Energy Commission and implemented by the Center for Sustainable Energy and CALSTART, provides rebates for EV charging infrastructure. Its Southern California Level 2 Incentive Project offers rebates of up to \$6,000 per connector (subject to project cost caps), and requires that at least 60 percent of funding be invested in Disadvantaged and Low-Income Communities. The Communities in Charge program, launched in late 2024 and continuing into 2026, prioritizes deployment of Level 2 EV charging at multi-family housing, Tribal lands, and other underserved community sites, offering incentives of roughly \$6,000 per connector with additional bonuses (e.g., for multi-family housing), subject to project cost caps. The Fast Charge California Project has supported DC fast charging infrastructure with substantially higher per-port incentives; while initial funding rounds have closed, additional solicitations may follow depending on future program funding. This state programmatic framework, identified for the City by resident Robert Farnsworth in 2025, is the foundation on which an Irvine fast-charging buildout should be constructed.

I recommend that the City commission a deployment plan to install DC fast charging at every Irvine public park, or at an optimal subset of parks selected to maximize geographic coverage and proximity to multi-family housing. Every multi-family complex of more than 50 units within the city should additionally receive City assistance (grant writing, permitting streamlining, and if necessary direct financing) in applying to CALeVIP and Communities in Charge for charging infrastructure at the site. This is, in my judgment, the most targeted and effective action the City can take for the equity of its climate transition, because multi-family residents are precisely the households for whom in-home charging is not available.

Renewable-powered mass transit: the case of Irvine CONNECT.

The Irvine CONNECT shuttle, launched April 2024, deserves close and honest examination. It is a free, public, fixed-route shuttle service using compressed natural gas (CNG) buses, with ridership of

approximately 141,000 boardings in its first year. It is an important equity and accessibility program. It is not currently a climate program.

A back-of-envelope analysis using standard emissions factors (on-road transportation factor of 0.393 kg CO₂e per vehicle-mile, derived directly from the 2019 inventory by dividing 1,144,205 MTCO₂e by 2.91 billion VMT; CNG bus direct tailpipe emissions of approximately 412 MTCO₂e per year for the current fleet schedule) and the program’s public ridership data suggests that Irvine CONNECT currently operates as a net source of greenhouse gas emissions, rather than a net reducer. The arithmetic is straightforward: the CNG buses run a fixed schedule regardless of ridership, while the passenger-trips displaced from private vehicles are limited by current ridership levels and by the fraction of riders who would otherwise have driven alone (research on free community shuttles typically finds this fraction at 20 to 40 percent). Under central-case assumptions, a 5-mile average trip length and a 30 percent car-trip replacement rate, the buses currently emit approximately 329 MTCO₂e per year more than they displace from private vehicles.

The path to making Irvine CONNECT a net carbon reducer is equally clear. Figure 1 displays, for three distinct scenarios, the relationship between annual boardings and net GHG impact, and identifies the "breakeven" ridership level at which net emissions reduction is achieved:

Figure 1. Net greenhouse gas impact of Irvine CONNECT as a function of annual boardings, under three fleet scenarios. The breakeven ridership at which the service transitions from net emitter to net reducer is approximately 699,000 boardings/year for the current CNG fleet, 119,000 boardings/year for an electric fleet on the current SCE grid, and 8,000 boardings/year for an electric fleet on 100% renewable electricity. Current ridership is approximately 141,000 boardings/year (dashed line).

Three conclusions follow from the figure, in my view decisively. First, with the current CNG fleet, achieving breakeven requires growing ridership by roughly a factor of five: from 141,000 boardings/year to

approximately 700,000. This is very ambitious, especially on the 2030 timeline of the ACHIEVES Resolution. Second, replacing the CNG fleet with battery-electric buses, even powered by the current SCE grid mix, brings the breakeven threshold down below current ridership; the service becomes a marginal net reducer immediately upon fleet electrification. Third, pairing an electric fleet with 100 percent renewable electricity through OCPA collapses the breakeven threshold to roughly 8,000 boardings/year, such that nearly any level of operation produces a substantial net carbon reduction. The dominant lever, by a wide margin, is fleet electrification, not ridership growth.

I therefore recommend two actions, in priority order:

- Prioritize the transition of the Irvine CONNECT fleet from CNG to battery-electric buses in the next vehicle procurement cycle. This single action flips the carbon equation from negative to positive at any ridership level achievable on the current service footprint. The CAAP's transportation measures TR-2 and TR-3 contemplate low- and zero-emission vehicle expansion; I urge the Council to direct staff to scope and fund fleet electrification as an explicit near-term action.
- In parallel, pursue a ridership target of 250,000+ annual boardings by 2028 through route expansion (UCI, the Irvine Business Complex, John Wayne Airport, the Great Park), service frequency improvements, and first-and-last-mile partnerships with OCTA and micromobility providers. Higher ridership compounds the carbon benefit of fleet electrification and strengthens the equity and mobility case that justifies the program in the first place.

With both levers engaged, Irvine CONNECT can become a net reducer of several hundred MTCO_{2e} per year, and potentially more as the service scales. This is still a small fraction of the 841,544 MTCO_{2e} in combined electricity and natural gas emissions that a fully decarbonized building sector would retire. I support and want to accelerate Irvine CONNECT on its own merits as an equity, mobility, and access program, but I do not want us to overstate its climate role, and I do not want the presence of a transit program to let us defer action on the larger building-sector and transportation-sector levers.

3. Trees Are Not Enough: A Quantitative Accounting

I want to address directly a question that arises naturally in community discussion of Irvine’s climate strategy: could we offset our emissions by simply planting more trees? The question deserves a numerical answer, not a rhetorical one. The answer is **no**. *Not even close*. I made this case to the City Council on September 9, 2025, during the Council’s consideration of Councilmember Treseder’s request to rescind the direction to submit notice of intent to withdraw from the Orange County Power Authority (agenda item 3.5). As Chair of the Sustainability Commission, I spoke on my own behalf in support of rescission. The full text of my public comment is included as Appendix C. The arithmetic I presented that evening is the starting point for this chapter.

3.1 The Urban Forest Master Plan

The City of Irvine’s Urban Forest Master Plan (UFMP) is a 30-year strategy, with the goal of achieving 30 percent city-wide canopy cover by 2055. Irvine’s current canopy cover is 21.9 percent, already a high level for cities in Southern California, and, as the UFMP notes, a testament to decades of deliberate master-planning choices that designated space for large trees to grow. Reaching 30 percent will require planting approximately 1,900 new trees per year for thirty years, totaling 67,500 net-new trees (19,000 on streets and in parks, 20,000 as part of the Great Park, and 28,500 on private property). The City manages just over 61,000 trees on public lands today and plans to spend on average \$2.29 million per year on contracted tree services (approximately 1 percent of the City’s total budget, nearly twice the national municipal average).

By every serious standard, Irvine’s urban forestry program is well-resourced, well-planned, and well-executed. What follows is in no way a criticism of that program. It is an argument about its proper role in the City’s climate strategy.

3.2 Per-Tree Carbon Sequestration

Urban trees sequester atmospheric carbon dioxide as they grow, with the annual rate depending strongly on tree age, species, climate, and maintenance regime. The peer-reviewed central estimate, based on research published by the U.S. Forest Service (Nowak and Crane 2002; Nowak et al. 2013), is that an average urban tree sequesters on the order of 48 pounds of CO₂ per year once mature, equivalent to approximately 0.022 MTCO₂e per tree per year. Vigorous, well-performing urban trees in favorable climates can reach 65 to 70 pounds per year, or approximately 0.030 MTCO₂e per tree per year, which is the rate implied by the 17-million-tree comparison I cited in my Council testimony.

I will use the more favorable figure of 0.030 MTCO₂e/tree/year throughout this chapter. I do this deliberately, so that the accounting below cannot be accused of stacking the deck against trees. At the more typical 0.022 MTCO₂e/tree/year rate, every number that follows becomes larger by roughly 37 percent, meaning the scale mismatch is, if anything, worse than what I present.

3.3 How Many Trees Would It Take?

The 2019 GHG Inventory found Irvine’s community-wide emissions at 2,247,593 MTCO₂e per year. Offsetting that total through urban tree sequestration alone would require:

2,247,593 MTCO₂e ÷ 0.030 MTCO₂e/tree/year ≈ 74.9 million new trees every year

This requires some reflection to absorb. Under the UFMP, the City plans to plant 1,900 trees per year. To offset community emissions with trees alone, we would need to plant approximately 39,500 times the UFMP rate—every year, forever—in a city with 61,000 total city-managed trees. The land area, the water resources, and the workforce required to plant and maintain roughly 75 million new trees annually exceed, by several orders of magnitude, any plausible use of the City’s physical footprint.

Irvine’s existing urban forest of 61,000 city-managed trees sequesters, under the same favorable assumption, approximately 1,830 MTCO₂e per year. *That is less than one-tenth of one percent of community emissions.* Figure 2 presents the full comparison on a logarithmic scale.

Figure 2. Trees Irvine currently has and is planning to plant (top two bars, green), compared with the number of trees required annually to offset each of Irvine’s major emissions sectors and total community emissions (lower four bars, red). **Note that the x-axis is logarithmic:** each gridline represents a factor of ten. Even at a favorable 0.030 MTCO₂e/tree/year mature-urban-tree sequestration rate, the offset calculations span six to seven orders of magnitude above Irvine’s actual planting capacity.

A tree is a good thing. Seventy-five million trees is not a policy.

3.4 What This Means for OCPA

The same arithmetic explains why Community Choice Energy is disproportionately consequential as a climate lever. Irvine's 2019 community-wide electricity emissions totaled 501,715 MTCO₂e. If every Irvine household and business purchased 100 percent renewable electricity through OCPA, the community would retire that full 501,715 MTCO₂e in a single policy step, one that requires no new equipment installation, no land use decisions, and no construction. At 0.030 MTCO₂e/tree/year, achieving the same reduction through trees alone would require $501,715 \div 0.030 \approx 16.7$ million new trees per year, rounded in my Council testimony to 17 million.

OCPA's 100 percent renewable tier, put differently, delivers the annual climate impact of planting approximately 17 million trees, *approximately 8,800 times the UFMP's annual planting rate of 1,900 trees, and approximately 270 times the entire existing stock of 61,000 city-managed trees.* On a per-year basis, *OCPA's renewable offering is nearly four orders of magnitude more impactful than the entirety of our urban forestry program.* This is not a rhetorical flourish; it follows directly from the per-tree sequestration rate and the community's measured electricity emissions.

3.5 The Policy Implication

None of this diminishes the value of the UFMP or of Irvine's long-standing commitment to urban forestry. Trees cool our streets and sidewalks; they mitigate the urban heat island effect that disproportionately harms our most vulnerable residents; they reduce stormwater runoff and flood risk; they support wildlife and pollinators; they improve mental health and quality of life; they beautify our neighborhoods; and yes, at a modest but real rate, they sequester carbon. Each of these benefits is independently valuable, and each justifies the UFMP on its own terms. We should plant the 1,900 trees per year the UFMP calls for, and we should exceed that target where we can.

What trees cannot do, at any realistic planting rate compatible with the physical dimensions of the City, is substitute for emissions reduction at the source. The math does not permit it. A climate strategy that leans on natural sequestration concedes the race before it begins. The City's path to honoring the ACHIEVES Resolution runs through the electricity grid, through the elimination of natural gas combustion in buildings, and through transportation electrification, not through planting.

On September 9, 2025, the Council voted to rescind the notice of intent to withdraw from the Orange County Power Authority. That decision, in my assessment, is among the most consequential climate actions the Council has taken since adopting the ACHIEVES Resolution itself. I restate the underlying arithmetic here because it is foundational to every other recommendation in this report: the City's single most important climate policy decision of the past decade remains our choice to join OCPA and to offer 100 percent renewable electricity for our community. Defending that decision against the current regulatory pressures described in Appendix A must remain a top priority.

4. Conclusion: Irvine Can Lead

Four decades ago, faced with scientific evidence that human activity was destroying the stratospheric ozone layer, the City of Irvine did not wait for the county, the state, the federal government, or the United Nations to act. Irvine banned chlorofluorocarbons within its own jurisdiction, the first municipality in the United States to do so. The *Los Angeles Times* called it “the most comprehensive law in the nation.” Other cities followed, then states, then the nation, then the world. The Montreal Protocol is today one of the most successful environmental treaties ever negotiated, and the ozone layer is recovering. *I do not think it is hyperbole to say that Irvine helped save our planet Earth.*

The climate crisis demands the same kind of action, at a larger scale and on a shorter timeline. Irvine has what it needs. We have a unanimous City Council commitment, in the ACHIEVES Resolution, to a zero-carbon local economy consistent with 2030 science. We have a completed GHG inventory that tells us exactly where the carbon is. We have a draft CAAP that identifies the right strategy areas. We have a voluntary Community Choice Energy authority capable of delivering 100 percent renewable electricity on demand. We have a small but real One Irvine program that can be scaled into a universal solarize-and-electrify financing engine. We have a sunny climate, a wealthy tax base, an educated citizenry, and a world-class research university within our borders.

What we do not yet have, and what this report calls for, is decision at pace. My recommendations are concrete: halt new gas infrastructure now; scale One Irvine into a universal Solarize-and-Electrify revolving loan by the end of 2027; launch a municipal EV purchase-loan program in 2027; deploy DC fast charging at every city park and multi-family site that will accept it; accelerate the transition of Irvine CONNECT to electric buses; and defend OCPA and the Community Choice Energy model against IOU-aligned regulatory capture at every available venue. None of these actions is speculative. All of them are already contemplated, in some form, in the CAAP or in the ACHIEVES Resolution itself.

If we do this, we will retire the overwhelming majority of our GHG emissions by 2030, keep approximately \$10 billion in twenty-year energy savings within our own economy, clean the indoor and outdoor air that our children breathe, and provide a replicable model for every other California city and every peer city in the country. Irvine has done this before. We can do this again. I hope that Earth Day 2026 is the moment we decide that we will.

Appendix A — Investor-Owned Utility Fee Structures and the Temporary Rise in CCE Rates

The recent, temporary increase in Community Choice Energy rates statewide, including at OCPA, is not, in my assessment, the result of CCE mismanagement or of genuine changes in the underlying cost of clean generation. It is the result of a specific regulatory decision by the California Public Utilities Commission (CPUC) that altered, retroactively, how an existing fee on every CCE customer's bill is calculated. I believe understanding this fee is essential context for the City's climate policy, because every additional dollar it adds to a CCE bill is a dollar of pressure to opt down to lower-renewable service or to return to investor-owned utility (IOU) bundled service.

A.1 The Power Charge Indifference Adjustment (PCIA)

The PCIA is a fee charged to every CCE customer in California to compensate the IOU for above-market costs of the legacy generation contracts the IOU entered into before CCE departure. The stated logic is that when a customer leaves IOU bundled service for CCE service, the IOU's remaining bundled customers should not be left holding the bag for long-term contracts procured on the departing customer's behalf. The PCIA methodology was substantially revised in 2018 and applied with periodic adjustments since, including in years when the formula produced charges that disadvantaged CCE customers. CCEs, including OCPA, accepted these outcomes as the cost of a working regulatory framework.

A.2 Decision 25-06-049 and the retroactive methodology change.

In 2024 and 2025, rising wholesale energy market prices increased the market value of IOU legacy portfolios. Under the existing PCIA formula, this would have shifted costs toward IOU bundled customers and reduced the PCIA charge on CCE customers. Before that outcome could take effect, the CPUC initiated an abbreviated four-month proceeding, with IOU support, and adopted Decision 25-06-049, which changed the methodology for calculating the market-price benchmarks used in the PCIA formula. The CPUC then applied this new methodology retroactively to 2025 rates that were already in effect.

The California Community Choice Association (CalCCA), the statewide association representing all 24 California CCAs including OCPA, has filed a Petition for Writ of Review with the California Court of Appeal challenging Decision 25-06-049, arguing that retroactive ratemaking is prohibited under California law and that the CPUC's justification relied on speculation rather than evidence that the pre-existing benchmark was flawed. In January 2026, CalCCA and member CCAs also filed rehearing petitions challenging the CPUC's approval of PG&E's and SCE's 2026 Energy Resource Recovery Account (ERRA) forecast applications on the same grounds.

A.3 Practical consequences for OCPA and for Irvine.

The PCIA is a pass-through charge outside OCPA's control. When the PCIA rises, OCPA has no option but to collect it. OCPA's Board has worked to hold its own generation rates steady for 2026, but the combined

effect of the PCIA increase and related ERRA decisions has, for many customer classes, eliminated or reversed the cost advantage that CCE service previously held over IOU bundled service. This creates customer-side pressure to opt down from the 100 percent Renewable Choice tier to the less-clean Basic Choice tier, or to return to SCE bundled service, undoing, one enrollment at a time, the greatest climate impact one household or business can that one decision can make.

A.4 Recommended advocacy positions.

This is a fairness issue that requires coordinated action. I respectfully recommend that the City consider the following:

1. Publicly support CalCCA's legal challenge to the retroactive PCIA methodology change and the associated rehearing petitions on SCE's 2026 ERRA forecast.
2. Send a formal letter from the Mayor and City Council to the CPUC urging fair, consistent, prospective application of the PCIA formula for all ratepayers.
3. Support state legislative efforts, including AB 1761 on PCIA transparency, that would require the CPUC to disclose the methodology, data inputs, and sensitivity analyses underlying PCIA calculations.
4. Coordinate with other Orange County cities participating in OCPA and with peer municipalities statewide to present a unified local-government voice to the CPUC and the Legislature.
5. Direct City staff, in collaboration with OCPA, to produce a quarterly public report on the dollar impact of PCIA changes on average Irvine residential and small-commercial bills, so that residents understand that OCPA is not the source of rate increases.
6. Engage the City's state delegation, State Senator Choi and Assemblymember Petrie-Norris representing Irvine, and the City's Congressman Dave Min on the question of IOU regulatory capture, as a matter of both climate policy and consumer protection.

The climate transition cannot succeed if the regulatory framework tilts cleaner providers' costs upward while shielding incumbent fossil-heavy providers from market discipline. The City of Irvine has, in my view, both the standing and the obligation to press this case.

Appendix B — References

City of Irvine, Resolution No. 21-50 (the ACHIEVES Resolution), 2021.

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Appendix C — Public Comment to the Irvine City Council, September 9, 2025

The following is the full text of the public comment I delivered to the Irvine City Council on September 9, 2025, during consideration of agenda item 3.5, a request by Councilmember Treseder to rescind direction to the City Manager to submit notice of intent to withdraw from the Orange County Power Authority. I spoke as Chair of the City of Irvine Sustainability Commission, on my own behalf. The 17-million-tree comparison cited in this testimony is the origin of the arithmetic developed in Section 3 of the present report.

“Good evening, Mayor and Councilmembers. My name is Dr. Kev Abazajian. I am Chair of the City of Irvine Sustainability Commission, Professor of Physics & Astronomy at UC Irvine, and a 14-year Irvine resident, speaking tonight on my own behalf. I urge you to rescind the letter of intent to withdraw from the Orange County Power Authority as requested by Councilmember Treseder.

Irvine has a proud, green legacy ... led often by Mayor Larry Agran. From banning CFCs decades ago to founding OCPA just five years ago, Irvine has shown bold leadership on the environment. And OCPA remains a critical tool in meeting our ambitious climate action goals.

As a physicist, I’m a numbers person. Here’s one striking number: OCPA’s renewable energy options for Irvine residents can deliver the same carbon-reduction impact as planting 17 million trees every year. Seventeen million. By contrast, our excellent urban forestry program aims to plant about 1,900 trees annually. As valuable as that effort is, it simply cannot rival the scale and immediacy of OCPA’s renewable energy. OCPA’s impact is up to a factor of 10,000 bigger than our forestry program.

OCPA empowers residents and businesses to choose cleaner energy that fits their needs ... whether the unmatched benefit of 100% renewable power, or other tiers that still beat the default utility. That flexibility ensures broad participation while steadily decarbonizing our community.

Leaving OCPA would take us backward. It would dismantle one of the most effective climate solutions available to us, and it would undercut Irvine’s reputation as a forward-thinking city. If we exit now, we forfeit our influence over OCPA’s future and abandon the leadership role we built as its founding city.

For the next generation of Irvine residents, the choice is clear: stay with OCPA and keep delivering the environmental equivalent of planting 17 million trees a year.

Thank you.”